

Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with 1,2-Dimethylethane-1,2-dionedihydrazone and Their Infrared and Electronic Spectra

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A number of investigations on metal complexes with vicinal dihydrazones having conjugated azomethine linkage have appeared in recent years¹⁻⁴ which contain five-membered chelate rings due to bonding through both the nitrogen atoms of the azomethine linkage, the nitrogen atoms of the amino groups remaining uncoordinated. The present communication describes the preparation, properties and characterisation of complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with 1,2-dimethylethane-1,2-dione-dihydrazone of the type, MLX_2 ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- or I^-) wherein nitrogen atoms of the amino groups have also participated in coordination.

Experimental

1,2-Dimethylethane-1,2-dione was of E. Merck quality and hydrazine hydrate of BDH make. All the compounds were prepared under similar experimental conditions described here.

Dichloro-1,2-dimethylethane-1,2-dionedihydrazone nickel(II), NiLCl_2 : 1,2-Dimethylethane-1,2-dione (1.7 g, 0.02 mol) in alcohol was treated with hydrazine hydrate (2.0 g, 0.04 mol) and the resulting mixture was warmed on a water bath for 10 min. The ligand solution thus obtained was added dropwise to an ethanolic solution of nickel(II) chloride hexahydrate (4.8 g, 0.02 mol) with constant stirring. The resulting mixture was refluxed for ~2 h on a water bath. The blue precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with alcohol, then with ether and finally dried at room temperature.

The compounds were analysed for metal, anion and hydrazine contents by standard procedures⁵. Physical measurements were carried out as reported earlier⁶. Analytical data for Ni, Co, N_2H_4 and anions were found to be in agreement with the formulae, MLX_2 within $\pm 1\%$.

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra of the complexes show marked similarity and are strikingly different from the spectra of the ligand as well as complexes of the type, ML_2X_2 ¹⁻³. A comparison of the spectra with those of the ML_2X_2 complexes suggests that although the general features of the spectra of the two classes are similar, marked differences are observed for NH_2 stretching and deformation

vibrations due to differences in the mode of coordination of the NH_2 groups.

In the spectra of the uncoordinated ligand, two bands appear in the region $3400\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH_2) with similar intensities which are assigned to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes. For ML_2X_2 complexes these two bands appear at slightly lower energies with reduced intensity and the changes are attributed to the coordination of the neighbouring imine nitrogen¹⁻³. In sharp contrast to these a group of three bands is observed in the spectra of the present complexes at ~ 3280 , ~ 3230 and $\sim 3130\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of the N-H stretching vibration of the coordinated NH_2 group. These are analogous to the NH_2 stretch for the bidentate hydrazine. Several earlier workers have assigned these bands, appearing in the region $3400\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ having similar characteristics, to the $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ of the coordinated NH_2 group. They occur at $50\text{--}100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ lower than the corresponding bands of uncoordinated hydrazine. The weakening of the N-H bonds is consequence of coordination of the nitrogen. The bands at $\sim 1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to the NH_2 . The other bands in the spectra of the complexes due to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-CH}_3}$ and $\delta_{\text{C-CH}_3}$ have features similar to the ML_2X_2 complexes³.

These results suggest that 1,2-dimethylethane-1,2-dionedihydrazone acts as a tetradentate ligand and the complexes may be postulated to have one of the two structures, Fig. 1(a) and 1(b).

Fig. 1(a)

Fig. 1(b): $\text{M} = \text{Co}^{II}$, Ni^{II} ; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , I^-

In the structure 1(a), the intermediate bis-complex acts as a coordinating agent through its terminal NH_2 groups on either side forming additional six-membered chelate rings. The remaining two coordination sites required for hexa-coordination being achieved by coordination with the X anions. However, in the latter case each metal ion forms a five-membered chelate ring with the

imine nitrogen atom of the 1,2-dimethylethane-1,2-dionedi-hydrazone and the terminal NH_2 groups coordinating to the neighbouring metal ions. As the bis-hydrazone complexes could not form any additional complex having the stoichiometry MLX_3 , the possibility of the complexes to possess the structure 1(a) is thus eliminated. Further evidence in support of structure 1(b) comes from the electronic spectral data.

The nickel(II) complexes having magnetic moment values in the range 3.00-3.15 B. M. manifest nearly octahedral coordination of ligand atoms about nickel(II) ions with $^3\text{A}_{2g}$ ground state under octahedral geometry or more precisely $^3\text{B}_{1g}$ under D_{4h} symmetry.

The spectra of the complexes show two bands in the region $14000\text{-}19000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a third band at $\sim 24000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These resemble the spectral features of NiL_2X_3 complexes implying that all the metal ion centres have similar ligand fields. Similar ligand fields would arise provided the complexes possess a polymeric structure 1(b) wherein each metal ion is coordinated to two imine nitrogen atoms and two NH_2 groups from the two adjacent molecules rather than the structure 1(a) wherein each bis-complex functions as ligands and bonding to metal ions on either side as an exo-bi-bidentate ligand. The structure 1(a) is expected to have two kinds of ligand fields about the metal ions and consequently the split components of the orbitally triplets in an octahedral field will have different energies leading to a larger number of electronic transitions as compared to the structure 1(b). The observed spectral data showing only three bands in the ligand field region lead us to believe that the complexes may have the structure 1(b). The three bands in the electronic spectra of the complexes are attributed to the transitions,

The cobalt(II) complexes possess magnetic moment values in the range 5.00-5.20 B.M. which correspond to an octahedral stereochemistry about the metal ion having the ground state ^4F which splits into $^4\text{T}_{1g}$, $^4\text{T}_{2g}$ and $^4\text{A}_{2g}$ whose energy levels increase successively and ^4P terms transforming as $^4\text{T}_{1g}$ under D_{4h} symmetry. One of the important features of the electronic spectra of the complexes is the appearance of a strong charge-transfer band above 20000 cm^{-1} and has in a few cases impeded resolution of the spectra in this region.

Though electronic spectra of several cobalt(II) complexes have been reported⁶⁻¹¹, their assignments have not been unambiguous. The ligand field transitions, $^4\text{A}_{2g} \leftarrow ^4\text{T}_{1g}$ and $^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P}) \leftarrow ^4\text{T}_{1g}$ appear in the visible region of spectra, the former being always weak, is scarcely observed. On the other hand, the latter appears as a relatively intense band with some amount of structure. The present cobalt(II) complexes exhibit a multiplet band

structure in the region $16000\text{-}19000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the band width spreading over *ca.* 3000 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to the transition $^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P}) \leftarrow ^4\text{T}_{1g}$. It may further be pointed out that the spectral features have similarity to the spectra of the bis-complexes, CoL_2X_3 implying similar ligand fields about the cobalt(II) ions providing evidence in favour of the structure 1(b) and ruling out the possibility of structure 1(a).

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Infrared Studies of Some Metal Periodates*

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PERIODATE ion is a very good oxidising and stabilizing agent. It can stabilize the unusual oxidation states of many transition metal ions. Very often periodates give insoluble compounds making them unsuitable for X-ray crystallographic studies. In these cases infrared study is very useful to characterise the bondings. In this attempt we have studied some periodate compounds of

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